

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF NATURAL PLANT FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

We utilize three kinds of natural fibres as reinforcement in plastic composites, derived respectively from bamboo culms, coconut husk (=coir) and marsh grass (*Phragmites*). All these natural reinforcing materials possess high cellulose content with reasonable strength and stiffness, but have been underexploited so far. Ten types of composites of different combinations of fibre phase and resin have been evaluated. All the test panels in this work show good application potentials as cheap but practical composite materials. We present a comparative analysis of the mechanical properties of these products under tensile, bending and compressive loading, and discuss fracture behaviour as well as relations between microstructure and properties.

Keywords: natural fibre composites; microstructure; mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

As adaptations to mechanical stresses imposed by environmental conditions, the anatomy of plants reveal definite structures of mechanical reinforcements. These can be found in the deposition of cellulose in thick-walled fibre cells, and hemicellulose and lignin in the walls of other types of thin-walled cells. In mechanical terms, a plant stem can be regarded as a natural composite material [1], with reinforcement by thick-walled fibre cells increasing centripetally forming a good support to withstand mechanical stress caused by wind, and is the reason why timber, for instance, is such a widely used resource. However, exploitation of plant fibres has been limited to large tree species, while the majority have not been fully utilised owing to their small size and susceptibility to biodegradation. Plant products such as bamboo culms, coconut husks and large grasses which have "strong" fibre reinforcements are such examples. In this paper we present our methods for fabricating these fibres into boards by suitable methods of fibre extraction and combination with resins and our findings on the mechanical properties of these. Although such products are inferior to present-day high performance fibre-reinforced materials, their specific strengths come out to be comparable to glass-fibre reinforced composites because they have densities of about 1g/cm^3 , and generally superior to wood yet are cheaper to produce than artificial fibre-reinforced composites, thus being of good

commercial potential.

We have reported upon the mechanical properties of bamboo and bamboo fibre reinforced composites in other publications [1-4]. This paper is a comparative analysis of the properties of composites which are reinforced with bamboo fibres, coconut husk fibres, and a marsh grass (*Phragmites* sp.) Here we report on their tensile, flexural, compressive and interlaminar shear properties and fracture behaviour. Particular emphasis is placed on relating the microstructure of these composite materials to their mechanical properties as well as failure modes. It should be mentioned that "fibre" here refers to the macroscopic fibres which are mechanically isolated from the bulk plant material and used in sample preparation. Microscopically these "fibres" are made up of many elongated "fibre cells". In our fabrication methods, the intercellular bonds between fibre cells have not been destroyed, and for consideration of mechanical properties, the macroscopic fibres are the units of reinforcement.

PREPARATION OF SPECIMENS

Three types of plant materials were used in this study: bamboo (*Bambusa* sp.), coconut husk, and the marsh grass (*Phragmites* sp.) By varying the processing method, we obtained short fibres, long fibres and chips from these plant materials to use in composite fabrication. Choice of resin included epoxy, resorcinol formaldehyde and urea formaldehyde. For preparation of bamboo fibres, the bulk plant material was first cut into thin strips and the strips passed between a pair of steel rollers to obtain fibre strands. Fibres were then separated by a stirrer. This method would increase the surface area of fibres in contact with the resin and provide better interfacial bonding. Bamboo chips were obtained by use of a wood planer. Coconut fibres were easily isolated from the husk material by a stirrer. As for *Phragmites*, essentially the stalk of the plant, after splitting between a pair of rollers, is used as reinforcement. In preparing specimens with long fibres, the fibre strands were spread over the mould in layers with sequential application of resin for each layer. Short fibres and chips were simply mixed with the resin mechanically. When resin content of the composites were increased beyond 30 - 40 weight % there was little improvement in mechanical properties. Thus the resin content of materials reported in this paper are limited to this magnitude.

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF PLANT FIBRE COMPOSITES

Table 1 is a summary of the mechanical properties of 10 natural fibre composites, some of which are based on our previous work [1-4]. Factors which affect mechanical performance include: the intrinsic mechanical properties of the plant fibres, the geometric morphology of the fibres, fibre content, properties of the resin matrix and fabrication conditions. Unidirectional long bamboo fibre reinforced epoxy specimens had the best tensile, compressive, bending and interlaminar shear properties, being similar to glass-fibre reinforced plastics, with specific tensile strength 3-4 times that of mild steel, 2-3 times better than hardwood. In general, reinforcement using bamboo chips, coconut husk (=coir) fibres, and grass (=Phragmites) fibres performed better than wood chipboard, with specific tensile strength being 2-6 times higher. In short bamboo fibre reinforced epoxy specimens, mechanical strengths were dependent on fibre length and generally higher (average 20% better) than when chipped bamboo was used, and performed 20 - 100% better than specimens reinforced with coir fibres and *Phragmites* fibres.

Comparing composites of identical resin type and fibre geometric morphology, the following hierarchy of performance is apparent: bamboo > coir > *Phragmites*. Such results are hardly

surprising in view of the different intrinsic strengths of these plant materials. The tensile strength of *Phragmites* : coir : bamboo fibres is 1 : 3 : 6. The tensile modulus of bamboo fibres is also about 6 times those of *Phragmites* and coir. Variations in the microanatomy of these fibre cells lend further support to this phenomenon. The diameters of the fibre cells of bamboo, coir and *Phragmites* are 16, 10 and 5 μm respectively. There is a further differentiation in the dispersion of these fibre cells within the different plants. Bamboo fibre cells are closely packed, thereby providing a large load-bearing cross-sectional area. Conversely coir fibre cells have a relatively larger internal lumen of approximately 3 μm diameter, and fibre cells found on the outer layers of the husk have ever greater lumen diameter.

In comparing the reinforcement capability of fibres of different geometrical morphology, the ranking was long fibres > short fibres > chips in all plant materials tested, when fabricated with the same resin. Long continuous fibres have the ability to transmit load along their length. When made into unidirectional composites, mechanical properties in the fibre direction are expected to be superior and thus give the best tensile properties. Bundles of fibres should best be separated by an appropriate process during fibre preparation. Figure 1 shows a bundle of coir fibre cells after separation from the husk material and Figure 2 the same before separation. The larger surface area available after separation for interfacial bonding with the resin is important in conferring strength and stiffness to the composite material. This aspect is especially relevant to interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength. We have found that short bamboo fibre reinforced epoxy samples were 3 times stronger than chipped bamboo reinforced epoxy samples (wherein the fibre is not particularly separated) in interlaminar shear strength, and that short bamboo fibre reinforced epoxy had 3 times the flexural strength of plywood and high quality wood chipboard.

The performance of the three resin types can also be ranked as follows: epoxy > resorcinol formaldehyde > urea formaldehyde. The comparative costs of these resins also reflect their mechanical performance. Scanning electron micrographs of chipped bamboo reinforced composites made from these three resins revealed that the chipped bamboo/epoxy sample had good interfacial bonding, while chipped bamboo/urea formaldehyde showed a degree of interfacial separation and some brittle fracture. Chipped bamboo/resorcinol formaldehyde was intermediate between the two.

Since an increase in the amount of fibre reinforcement will improve mechanical performance, and this can be done at low relative costs in case of these plant fibres, resin content can be economized to allow sufficient bonding rather than an excess in the fabrication of these composite materials. In the fabrication process, surface treatment of fibres, moulding pressure, moulding temperature and moulding time can also be varied according to fibre geometrical configuration and the nature of the resin. Finally, a judicious choice of fibre species can produce materials for different applications. One example is *Phragmites* fibre, which in unidirectional long fibre composites had overall inferior performance compared to bamboo fibre composites, yet had better tensile strength than chipped bamboo and coir composites. Furthermore, it is probably the least costly of the fibres tested in this study and has potential for manufacturing for specific uses.

FAILURE MODES OF PLANT COMPOSITE MATERIALS

The elastic moduli of bamboo fibre composites are several decades in GPa, and has good toughness [5] ($K_T = 3 - 4 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$). During failure, multiple fractures and elongation are significant (tensile strain = 4%). Fibre pullout and fibre breakage can be seen, and delamination was obvious. Figures 3 - 4 are examples of fracture micrographs of BLF/EP [0] subjected to

compressive and bending stresses in the loading stage of a scanning electron microscope. In [0] samples, cracks at notch front propagate along the 0° surface (Fig. 5). This type of failure mode is similar to that of glass fibre and carbon fibre reinforced composites.

For coir fibre composites, stiffness is only about one-tenth that of bamboo composites, but coir fibres have good elasticity, and failure starts first by destruction of interfacial bonds. Under higher tensile stress, damage by shear gives fracture surface at close to 45° in relation to stress direction. Figure 6 shows the cross section of a fractured coir fibre reinforced urea formaldehyde sample where fibre pullout and resin penetration is apparent.

Phragmites composites are comparatively brittle. Owing to the small fibre cell diameter and the presence of a waxy substance surrounding fibre bundles, interfacial bonding was weak, and interlaminar shear strength was low. Figure 7 shows the delamination and transverse cracking occurring in a PH/UF [0] sample with little deformation. Figure 8 shows the brittle fracture of 2 bundles of *Phragmites* fibre cells.

CONCLUSION

In terms of overall performance, the composite materials investigated in this study would rank as follows: long bamboo fibre > short bamboo fibre > chipped bamboo fibre > coir fibre > *Phragmites* fibre. Shear strength and compressive strength is strongly related to the intrinsic properties of different resins, with epoxy performing better than resorcinol formaldehyde and urea formaldehyde ranking third.

Different plant sources yield fibres of varying properties, and "high" performance fibres such as bamboo can be exploited in the manufacture of load bearing products, which can potentially replace hardwood and glass fibre reinforced composites. Chipped bamboo, coir and *Phragmites* fibres can be fabricated into boards with higher performance than wood chipboard, and has the potential of becoming a new commercial product of wide domestic applications. The strategic exploitation of waste and surplus cellulose fibres occurring naturally or as agricultural by-products is here advocated as a useful development in composite material manufacture.

References

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Table 1. Mechanical Properties of Natural Plant Fibre Reinforced Plastic Composite Materials.
 (B - Bamboo, CH - coir, PH - *Phragmites*; LF - long fibres, SF - short fibres, C - chip;
 EP - epoxy, RF - resorcinol formaldehyde, UF - urea formaldehyde; Wm - resin content by weight;
 f.l. - fibre length)

Material	Detail	Density (g/cm ³)	Tension			Specific Tensile Strength cm x 10 ³	Compression		Flexure		Interlaminar Shear Strength (MPa)
			Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	✓		Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	
BAMBOO	dried	0.8	88-142	8.7-17.7		11.3-16.3	73-75		113-152	9.1-12.3	12-20
BLF/EP	[0] 3-7 ply	1.18	178-243	45-76	0.38	15.3-30	59-129	24.9-25.4	208-255	16.4-24.9	10-17
BLF/UF	[0]	1.06		9.8-2.5					142-248		
BLF/EP	[0/90]	1.18	98	17	0.20	8.3	54	25	135	14.1	
BSF/EP	f.l. 3-6cm	1.17	19-49	3.7-8.2	0.32	1.6-4.2			72-103	6.8-8.6	10-12
BC/EP	Wm 20-30%	1.26	24-32	8.6	0.23	1.9-2.5	44-54		73	8.9	
BC/RF	Wm 20-30%	1.15	17-26	6.1-7.5	0.22	1.5-2.2	39-51	3.2-3.5	36-70	5.9-9.2	5.4
BC/UF	Wm 17-20%	1.14	15-24	5.0-8.7	0.20	1.6-2.1		1.0-2.3	15-52	3.6-8.1	3.6
CH/UF	Wm 30-40%	1.15	18-21	2.9-3.1	0.27	1.6-1.8			22-28	2.5-3.8	2.3-3.9
CHSF/UF	Wm 17-27%	0.93	14-21	2.9-3.5	0.41	1.5-2.3			34-55	2.6-2.8	3.8-5.9
PH/UF	Wm 17-25%	0.98	19-30	2.2-3.2	0.58	1.9-3.1			15-23	1.3-2.2	2.1

Figure 1. Disposition of coir fibre cells showing effectiveness of mechanical separation.

Figure 2. A bundle of coir fibre cells before separation.

Figure 3. Compressive failure of BLF/EP [0] specimen.

Figure 4. Flexure failure of BLF/EP [0] specimen.

Figure 5. Crack propagation of BLF/EP [0] specimen.

Figure 6. Fibre pullout and resin penetration in CH/UP specimen.

Figure 7. Interlaminar shear failure and transverse cracking of PH/UF specimen.

Figure 8. Brittle fracture of two bundles of *Phragmites* fibres.